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FEATURES OF CLINICAL MANIFESTATION AND WAYS TO SOLVE THE PROBLEM OF DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY IN CHILDREN

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Relevance. *Diabetic nephropathy (DN) and its progression to chronic renal failure (CRF) have become an important issue of national health in Europe, the USA and Japan. In terms of the need for hemodialysis treatment or kidney transplantation, DM ranks first in the USA and shares 2nd and 3rd place in European countries. In the USA, the main contribution to the annual increase in the number of patients with CRF (8%) is made by patients with DM, estimated at 34% of all cases [14].*

Until recently, most cases of CRF were identified with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM). The prevalence of DN and CRF in non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) has not been sufficiently studied, since it is difficult to accurately determine the time of disease onset, and increased albumin excretion can be observed even with a short duration of the disease. This situation is gradually beginning to change, since it is increasingly difficult to ignore the growing number of patients and the cost of all types of medical care aimed at combating this complication of diabetes. Terminal renal failure in type 2 diabetes develops much less frequently than in type 1 diabetes (5-10% and 30-50% of cases, respectively). However, these patients make up 90% of the entire diabetic population, and CRF that develops as a result of DN is the second most common cause of death (after cardiovascular complications). The US National Foundation has published data showing that patients with type 2 diabetes now account for the same number of new cases of chronic kidney disease as patients with type 1 diabetes [1].

Keywords: *diabetic nephropathy, glomerular filtration rate, renal threshold.*

Kidney damage in type 2 diabetes 1. Specific kidney damage (diabetic nephropathy proper):

diffuse glomerulosclerosis, nodular glomerulonephritis.

2. Non-specific kidney damage

- Infectious: bacteriuria, pyelonephritis, renal carbuncle, renal abscess, papillary necrosis.
- Vascular: atherosclerotic nephrosclerosis, hypertensive nephrosclerosis.

- Toxic: when administering contrast agents, abuse of non-narcotic analgesics.
- Neurogenic: atony of the bladder (hydronephrosis).
- Immunoinflammatory: glomerulonephritis, interstitial nephritis.
- Tumor: paraneoplastic nephropathy.
- Urolithiasis.

Kidney damage in type 2 diabetes mellitus is represented by a wide spectrum, in which diabetic glomerulosclerosis, pyelonephritis and urinary tract infection, atherosclerotic nephrosclerosis, hypertensive nephrosclerosis have the greatest clinical significance. These changes are primarily associated with the peculiarities of metabolic disorders in diabetes mellitus with characteristic micro-macroangiopathy, a tendency to infectious complications and an increased risk of cardiovascular pathology. The prevalence and severity of kidney damage are also affected by oncological diseases and iatrogenic factors. We should not forget about glomerulonephritis - one of the most common causes of chronic renal failure in our country. Peculiarities of kidney damage in type 2 diabetes may be due to age-related morphological changes, such as sclerosis of small renal arteries and arterioles (especially efferent) with hyperperfusion of the medulla and a decrease in the cortical fraction, fibrosis of the interstitium of the medulla, and focal glomerulosclerosis. These changes lead to a decrease in the activity of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system and a decrease in the synthesis of prostaglandins, which is manifested by a gradual (starting from the age of 40) decrease in acidogenesis, the concentrating ability of the kidneys, the reabsorption of water and sodium chloride, and a decrease in the renal effect of antidiuretic hormone. A decrease in the filtration function of the kidneys (slower than the concentrating ability) is associated with a decrease in cortical blood flow (by 10% every decade) and the progression of glomerulosclerosis so that by the age of 80 the total number of glomeruli decreases almost twofold. In addition to age-related renal hemodynamic disorders, favorable background conditions include decreased immune reactivity, impaired urodynamics (hypokinesia of the ureters, bladder, prostate adenoma), hypertension, hyperlipidemia with established "nephrotoxic" action of lipids [9, 16]. Even moderately expressed effects of dysmetabolism created by diabetes can decompensate the kidney in elderly people. In type 2 diabetes, the same dependence of the incidence of DN on the duration of the disease is observed as in type 1 diabetes; however, the course and clinical manifestations of DN differ. Hyperfiltration, which is characteristic of the early stages of DN in patients with type 1 diabetes, i.e. high glomerular filtration rate (more than $140 \text{ ml/min} \cdot 1.73 \text{ m}^2$), is not detected in patients with type 2 diabetes, which is probably associated with the severity of sclerotic changes in the renal tissue already at the onset of the disease in the latter [7]. Hyperfiltration is detected in Pima Indians with diabetes (a kind of natural model of NIDDM) and microalbuminuria [10] (ethnic

differences in the population of patients with diabetes may play a role; the young age of the Indians allows them to avoid multimorbidity). Microalbuminuria in patients with type 1 diabetes is the most important harbinger of the clinical stage of DN, in patients with type 2 diabetes this indicator is more associated with the development of cardiovascular pathology [8]. 55-60% of patients with diabetes mellitus and microalbuminuria die from myocardial infarction or stroke, and only 3-5% from uremia. Microalbuminuria is not only and not so much a predictor of renal disease (as in type 1 diabetes mellitus), but a marker of atherosclerosis and premature death. The causes of increased cardiovascular mortality have not been fully clarified. This may be a consequence of more severe, generalized endothelial dysfunction predisposing to atherosclerosis, a sign of which is microalbuminuria [13]. The development of microalbuminuria in diabetes mellitus is associated with abnormalities in the hemostasis system, coagulation, and glucose and lipid metabolism. Recent studies have shown that microalbuminuria may be an independent manifestation of cardiometabolic syndrome X [5]. Thus, the definition of microalbuminuria for the diagnosis of DN in diabetes mellitus is not specific. In contrast, macroalbuminuria makes the diagnosis of DN more likely, especially in the presence of retinopathy [3]. A number of studies on the study of structural changes in the kidneys in diabetes mellitus with microalbuminuria revealed a heterogeneous picture [2, 4]. Only a third of patients had a typical picture of diabetic glomerulosclerosis, characteristic of DN in diabetes mellitus. Normal or close to normal kidney structure was also determined in a third of patients; a third of patients had "atypical" patterns of renal damage with the absence or minor glomerular changes against the background of disproportionate tubulointerstitial changes, arterial hyalinosis and global sclerosis. If in type 1 diabetes mellitus the diagnostic criteria and staging of DN are outlined, then in type 2 diabetes mellitus this is difficult. Each case of nephropathy is individual, especially for the elderly. There are very few studies in the literature devoted to the systematic determination of predictors of the development and progression of DN in patients with diabetes mellitus. The most probable are poor glycemic control, arterial hypertension, urinary tract infection, hyperlipidemia, and genetic factors [6, 11, 16]. Therapeutic approaches at different stages of DN in type 2 diabetes have their own characteristics. In the early subclinical stage of the disease, when it is possible to influence its morphological substrate, the primary role among therapeutic measures belongs to glycemic control and its stabilization at an optimal level [12, 15]. This approach is important, since it is of decisive importance for eliminating intrarenal hemodynamic disorders that initiate diabetic glomerulosclerosis. The pathological significance of hyperglycemia is also manifested in non-enzymatic glycation of proteins, the polyol pathway of glucose metabolism, impaired synthesis of glycosaminoglycans, and, finally, direct glucose

toxicity. Treatment of diabetes, especially in the elderly, often remains unsatisfactory. Poor glycemic control is typical for this age group. Doctors sometimes do not take into account the different needs of these patients, their attitude towards the disease, social conditions and individual difficulties in compliance with dietary recommendations, exercise and medication. Despite these limitations, there is sufficient evidence that good control is a reasonable goal with real short-term and long-term benefits. Given the role of chronic decompensation of diabetes in the development of vascular complications, strict criteria for diabetes compensation, all patients should be trained in the principles of diabetes therapy and self-monitoring of carbohydrate metabolism. At the initial stage of DN in diabetes, all hypoglycemic drugs of the sulfonylurea group, biguanides, and glucosidase blockers can be used, provided that satisfactory compensation of carbohydrate metabolism is maintained. At the stage of advanced DN, especially with declining renal function, when irreversible, advanced morphological changes occur, the requirements for achieving ideal compensation of carbohydrate metabolism are weakened. Moreover, the desire to maintain ideal compensation of diabetes in patients with severe DN is associated with the risk of hypoglycemia against the background of a decrease or complete disappearance of precursor symptoms. At the stage of CRF, transfer to insulin therapy is mandatory, since most oral hypoglycemic agents are metabolized and excreted by the kidneys. An exception is glurenorm (gliquidone, Boehringer Ingelheim, Austria), excreted through the biliary tract, which allows its use in patients at the initial stage of CRF. With the development of CRF, certain difficulties in controlling carbohydrate metabolism arise due to changes in the need for insulin. On the one hand, with nephrosclerosis, the need for exogenous insulin administration decreases due to a violation of its metabolism. This is also facilitated by intoxication, diabetic paresis of the gastrointestinal tract and subsequent impaired absorption of food. If this is not addressed, there is a risk of hypoglycemia, and due to autonomic neuropathy, patients lose the ability to feel its clinical manifestations. With CRF, tissue resistance to insulin increases, which is eliminated with the start of dialysis therapy. Dialysis stops dyspeptic symptoms, improves appetite, which increases the need for insulin. Glycemic control in each patient is quite complex and should be carried out individually. It is generally accepted that a hemodialysis session does not dramatically change the need for insulin. It is recommended to use a dialysate containing glucose at a concentration of 200 mg% in diabetes mellitus, which reduces the risk of both hyper- and hypoglycemia. Metabolic control in DN at the stage of CRF is extremely important in the complex of therapeutic measures, since inadequate glycemic control initiates a tendency to infectious complications and can lead to a sharp increase in the volume of extracellular fluid, including the thirst mechanism. Issues of compensation for diabetes in DN are complex

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